

Response Letter to Retrieving SSH Journals Citation Information from three datasets (COCI, META and ERIH-PLUS) – Workflow v1 Reviews

First, we would like to thank our colleagues Maddalena Ghiotto¹ and Sebastiano Giacomini² for the useful reviews they have provided us.

Taking into consideration the suggestions made in their reviews, we have modified our workflow adding more details on both the data management and the methodology used in our research.

We have added information about the software requirements (e.g., Python version and specific libraries). In addition, we have also given detailed and specific information about the structure of the input data, giving practical examples of them. We have also described in detail, with examples, the outcome we have obtained after the preprocessing and processing of data, by analyzing also the methods needed to perform such actions and obtain such outputs.

For what concerns the FAIR data treatment of our data, it is not mentioned in the protocol since it is stated in the DMP.

We have modified the abstract, even if some information that our colleagues didn't find in it were already present, such as the reason why scholars should work on these datasets.

Finally, we have added more information on the final formats of the output data. We didn't mention any intended visualization of data because we still need to define the final procedure for answering to the questions.

¹ Maddalena Ghiotto. (2023). Review of: "Retrieving SSH Journals Citation Information from three datasets (COCI, META and ERIH-PLUS) - Workflow v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/0FZCPH.

² Sebastiano Giacomini. (2023). Review of: "Retrieving SSH Journals Citation Information from three datasets (COCI, META and ERIH-PLUS) - Workflow v1". Qeios. doi:10.32388/LJL963.